

DEFICIENCY IN INSURANCE SERVICES UNDER THE CPA, 2019

by

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1.1. ABSTRACT

The advantages of insurance are being increasingly realized by people all over the world. For instance, everybody is aware that life insurance not only inculcates the habit of saving but also provides protection and security to the insured. However, it needs to be seen whether the insurance companies have also achieved consumer satisfaction. It is only when there is deficiency in the service rendered and they'd suffered any loss/ injury due to the negligence of the insurers that relief by way of compensation can be granted. Redressal forum under 3-tier is established by the GOI for resolving claims and disputes. Mere delay with furnishing reasonable grounds for such does not amount for non-settlements of claims. The offence and penalties for the misrepresentation will be punished with imprisonment for 2 years or more & fine 10L or more and for every subsequent offence as well accordingly.

Key Words- Insurance services deficiencies, claim settlement delay.

CHAPTER-I

PRELIMINARY

1.2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The information compiled into this research paper is from various independent internet resources, newspaper, case law and research article as well with laws book itself. one of the leading finance newspapers describes about the changes made to the Insurance Ombudsman scheme for better resolution of complaints. One of the authors of the article describes about the redressal mechanism provided to the insured under the CPA,2019. In one of the leading books of law, the author explains about the deficiencies of services by the insurer under the Companies following the consequences of that as such. The bare Acts of the consumer protections provides the very legal definitions of the related terms mentioned herein under this paper. Various judgements regarding deficiencies are further explained in detailed and other details of Information are further discussed via Research structure under this Paper.

1.3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The present study intended to focus upon the issues and problems relating to deficiencies of services provided by the insurance company to the insured individuals via offering various policies. Besides, the study also endeavoured to find as to what are the key factors/conditions under which the complaints can be filed with the CPA,2019. The issues of services deficiencies in respect of non-settlement of claims are further explained via significant judgments. Finally, the study also took a critical view of the need for strengthening the very regulatory laws regarding the functioning of the insurer. The study has been geared by the key Fact that deficiencies of services not only impair the justice mechanism but also proves to be ineffective for carrying of their intention that is to indemnify and protecting the insured from loss/damage or Injury as such.

1.5. OBJECTIVE

1. To study the Deficiencies of insurances services and conditions under which complaints in respect so to be filed.
2. To examine basics regarding Insurance services and Role of CPA,2019 and the Important Judgements in respect of non-settlement of claims as deficiencies in services by the insurer.
3. To provide few modifications/suggestions in respect of improvements if so necessary.

1.6. HYPOTHESIS

1. Insurance is a valuable risk-financing tool. Services are provided by the Insurance companies to insured against financial risk/loss via various insurance policy. Deficiencies need to fall with the defined ambient of law, only then claim for settlements can be addressed.
2. Deficiencies by the insurer in rendering their services via such policy gives rise to legal disputes/complaints which are dealt under the CPA,2019. However, with recent amendment to the Insurance ombudsman scheme such can be dealt under that also by the policyholders.
3. Delays in Intimidating about damage/loss of product so insured under the policy is not a necessary ground for non-settlement of claims.

1.7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In respect of objective, doctrinal research design has been adopted. The paper will be based from newspapers articles and research articles. The information will be collected from primary and secondary sources such as books, and independent internet resources, websites, case laws, statutes and bare Acts. This research paper is based purely on theoretical aspects and focuses towards the analysis of insurance services Deficiency and how delays in rendering of justice regarding the claim settlement impacts the party so insured along with redressal mechanism so provided and also derives the answers for the research problem related thereof.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

CHAPTER-II

INSURANCE SERVICES AND CONSUMER PROTECTION LAWS

2.1. INSURANCE SERVICES

Insurance is the basic necessity that human seeks to protect themselves/ family/assets/ property from any kind of financial Risk or losses in general which are unforeseen/ uncertain in nature and arises at any given point of time in life. Insurance plays a huge role in Risk Management as well and is a valuable risk-financing tool. Few organizations have the reserves or funds necessary to take on the risk themselves and pay the total costs following a loss. Therefore, services are provided by the companies for such against the loss via insurance policy which differs in the products and varies from region to region. The most common types involve the protection for property such as vehicle/house insurance policy. The other Insurance services offered are contract to protect Life, reimbursements of health care costs etc.¹

2.2. INSURANCE UNDER CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT,2019.

As there exists a contractual relationship & obligations between the insured & insurer Consumer fall under the ambit of Consumer Protection Act,2019. The sole purpose/object of the Act (New and Old) is to safeguard the Interest of the consumer and to protect them against all kinds of exploitation in market place.² Therefore, when a consumer detects any defect or deficiency in the services provided by the other party say insurer then under such circumstances, they can lodge a complaint against them. However, the deficiency must fall within the ambit of definition/meaning as provided under the CPA. Under the act of 2019, there has been a major and significant inclusion of Product Liability and action which provides the consumer can file a complaint under it too in respect of deficiency in services or products.³ The offence and penalties for the misrepresentation which is prejudicial to the interest of consumers by service provider will be punished with imprisonment for 2 years or more & fine 10L or more and for every subsequent offence, with 5 years or 50L.⁴ Consumer Courts is a 3-tier system of courts (National level, State level and District level) where aggrieved consumers can approach as per the valuation of matter in concern, for redressal and adjudication of disputes.⁵

CHAPTER-III

¹ VOL.3, THE INSTITUTE OF COMPANIES SECRETARIES OF INDIA, INSURANCE LAW & PRACTICE, 12, Delhi Computer Services, 2014.

² The Consumer Protection Act, No.35, Acts of Parliament,2019 (India)

³ Dandodiary, <https://www.dandodiary.com/2019/10/articles/consumer-protection/guest-post-india-the-consumer-protection-act-2019-exposures-liability-insurance-protection/>, March 31st 2021.

⁴ Supra Note 2

⁵ Priyanka Bhatra & Nishtha Das, Deficiency of services under CPA,2019, Mondaq, Aug. 24th 2020,

<https://www.mondaq.com/india/dodd-frank-consumer-protection-act/978694/deficiency-of-services-under-consumer-protection-act-2019?>

DEFICIENCY IN INSURANCE SERVICES

3.1. DEFICIDENCY OF SERVICES

The CPA recognises physical relationship of buyer-seller and where this exists so does deficiency and any grievances as such against services one can reach out for redressal. The consequences can array from inconvenience/ harassment to mental /physical damage or death, thereby leading to legal consequences.⁶

According to Sec. 2(11) deficiency refers to the any kind of fault/imperfection/shortcoming or inadequacy in quality/nature/performance undertaken to be maintained or performed in reference to contract or services. It also includes act of omission/commission/negligence or withholding relevant Info. By any such person which would in-turn cause loss or Injury to the Consumer. In another Words Only upon deficiency and suffering of loss or Injury due to the negligence of the insurers from such service the compensation can be granted. Both the Govt /private body are liable under the Act to provide relief to the aggrieved party.

Sec. 2(10)- Defect refers to fault/ imperfection /shortcoming in the quality/ quantity/potency/ purity/ standard which is required to be maintained under the contracts or as is claimed by the trader in any manner whatsoever in relation to any goods or product.

Sec. 2(34) and (35)- defines product liability and action- meaning the responsibility of service provider to compensate for any harm caused to consumer by deficiency in services, for not issue adequate instructions or warnings, did not conform to express warranty or the terms and conditions of the contract AND a complaint by a person before District/State /National Commission for claiming compensation for the harm caused to him can be filed respectively

Sec.2(42)- service in terms of insurance can be defined as description regarding facilities being made available to the users such as of financing /banking /insurance but does not include rendering such services free of charge or under personal contract basis.⁷

3.2. REMEDIES AVAILABLE

The aggrieved party has the following remedies available with them: a) firstly, go to grievance redressal mechanism of the service provider. b) legal notice can be given before approaching consumer court. c) if the two first steps fail, then legal course of action can be taken in the forum. The time frame available for filing the complaint is within 2 years for deficiency in services and further can be expanded on the basis of circumstances of the case so satisfied.⁸

CHAPTER-IV

⁶ Akanksha Bhattarai, Deficiency in service under consumer protection Act,2019, Latest-law, Feb 25th 2021, [https://www.latestlaws.com/articles/deficiency-in-service-under-consumer-protection-act-2019/#:~:text=Section%20%20\(11\)%20of%20Consumer,performed%20by%20a%20person%20in](https://www.latestlaws.com/articles/deficiency-in-service-under-consumer-protection-act-2019/#:~:text=Section%20%20(11)%20of%20Consumer,performed%20by%20a%20person%20in)

⁷ The Consumer Protection Act, S. 2(11),(10), (34) ,(35), 9420, No.35, Acts of Parliament,2019 (India)

⁸ Supra Note 6

IMPORTANT JUDGEMENTS REGARDING INSURANCE SERVICES

DEFICIENCY

4.1. GURSHINDER SINGH v. SRIRRAM GENERAL INSURANCE CO. LTD AIR 2020 SC 65

Facts of the case- The tractor (Vehicle) so insured by the appellant from the respondent's company was stolen, FIR was filed however there was delay of 52 days to intimate the same to the insurance Company and they refuse to settle the claim on the same grounds. Accordingly, matter went to District Consumer Disputes Redressal Forum, Punjab dispute was settled with awarding compensation in accordance with the vehicle value so insured. Aggrieved from the order the company went to state and then to national redressal whereby order of district forum was set aside. Aggrieved by that appellant moved to the SC.

Question of law- whether delay in intimating the information regarding theft despite of FIR lodged would disentitle the claim of appellant?

Judgement- -- From analysing the conditions laid down under **commercial vehicle policy** AND from relying on the case laws- **Om Prakash vs. Reliance General Insurance & Anr** SC stated that that all relevant info regarding the theft, FIR should be filed with police first and then the role of the Insurance company comes into place upon failure to find by the police. Mere delay in informing to the insurer when the same is done to the Law enforcement wouldn't amount to breach of 'duty to cooperate' of the insured. Claimant cannot be denied merely on the technical ground of intimation delay to the respondent. it would be unfair and unreasonable to reject genuine claims which had already been verified and found to be correct. Thus, relying Upon such direct forum order was upheld & appellant was compensated accordingly⁹

4.2. MAINA DEVI BAIRALIA v. LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION AIR 1993 NCDR

Facts of the case- The husband of the Appellant took a life insurance policy from the company, however he failed to pay one of yearly premium dues and before he could do so died from the illness. Claim was lodged by appellant with the Corporation under such policy, despite various letters, newspaper publishing, legal notices however they neglected and delayed in rendering their services for more than 15 years and settling the claim amount. Letter to Finance Minister were also written. Hence matter for was filed before the NCDR.

⁹Gurshinder Singh V. Sriram General Insurance Co. Ltd. AIR 2020 SC 65

Question of law- Whether the nature of the Final claim settlement by the appellant is genuine or not?

Judgement- The NCDR stated that corporation action was highly negligent and unfair in performing its services as for more than 15 years the Nominee being a widow have to go through hardships. Regarding the allegations that she had suppressed material facts about illness were not investigated, repudiated by the corporation at that time nor it was brought to the notice of Appellant. voucher sent for execution to the Complainant was signed in utter frustration and coercion due to delay/and lapses from the corporation. Thus, NCDR settled the claim of the Appellant with @12% interest per annum with the original claim.¹⁰

4.3. SUKHJINDER SINGH v. NEW INDIA ASSURANCE CO. LTD AIR 2021 DCRC

Facts of the case- The truck of the Complaint was insured with the insurance company; all legal formalities were absolute. However, it got stolen in 2017 on the watch of helper named Gurcharan and every possible effort were made to trace it. upon notifying the same to the company with delay of 622 days i.e., 2019 they advised to lodge an FIR but the Intimation of that was rejected by the respondents due to lack of Information regarding the Vehicle particulars and with duplicate RC, FIR was again lodged, Non-traceable certificate was received and same was intimidated to the company. Despite repeated visits, the respondent didn't settle the claim and refuted it to be non-payable which was not even repudiated to the appellant. For the deficiency in services and unfair trade practices the complaint was filed.

Question of law- whether the theft of vehicle on part of negligence by the third party of appellant give rise to claim settlement?

Judgement- while relying upon the case of **Kailash Chandrakant Bhalerao and Anr. V ICICI Lombard general Insurance Co. Ltd. AIR 2015-** the commission stated that from the averments made by the Respondents it was clear that the appellant was in breach of contract with multiple breach of the terms and conditions of the policy and insurance company so insured such as changing the names of the drivers, no driving licence production delaying with almost 2 years in intimidating about the theft, keeping the vehicle unsupervised condition hence being negligent on their own part. Thus, the Insurance company was not in deficiency of its services and according the claim of the appellant wasn't settled.¹¹

4.4. LEGAL MEASURES TO PROTECT POLICYHOLDERS

¹⁰ Maina Devi Bairalia v. Life Insurance Corporation AIR 1993 NCDR

¹¹ Sukhjinder Singh V. New India Assurance Co. Ltd AIR 2021 DCRC

In respect of improvising the Insurance Mechanism in order to facilitate better resolution of Complaints Regarding services Deficiencies, the UOI amended the Ombudsman scheme of 2017. In the new amended scheme, there is an enlarged scope provided with respect to the complaints as Complaints regarding Services deficiencies especially delay in settlement of claims in respect of the life/general insurance policies on part of Insurers, brokers and other intermediaries can now be filed against them and under it. This can be done electronically, hearings via video conferencing, status can be checked online by the Policyholders. It is less time consuming, cost-effective and impartial in nature. Thus, with such amendment positive reformatory or outcomes can be seen in the near future.¹²

Thus, from the Above Information it is to be understood that one of the most important principles, under insurance is that of Indemnity and Consumer satisfaction in time of claim settlements. The need to be compensated/ indemnified for loss/damage suffered is the very basis of insurance. The speed and ease with which it is done also hallmarks the very purpose of Insurance. Deficiency of services by this Insurance companies can happen at given point of time or under circumstances which can lead to delay in justice for the Insured person. However as seen in new India Assurance there is a flip side to the coin as well. Any Individual having an authority of power or laws can misuse and mislead each other for claim settlement as well. Therefore, Regulatory measures are for such situations are also the way to reap the Benefits from such seed sowed.

CHAPTER -V

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

¹² Sanjeev Sinha, Deficiency in insurance services: Govt amends ombudsman rules for better resolution of policyholders, financial-express, march 3rd 2021, 3:32PM, <https://www.financialexpress.com/money/insurance/insurance-better-resolution-of-policyholders-complaints/2207441/>

After done with through analysis and research on the topic of Insurance services deficiencies and their consequences under the consumer protection act it can be concluded that the insurance act is in compliant with the object/statement of reasons with that of the CPA,2019 i.e., both works in favour to protect and safeguard the interest of the insured person or the consumer from their exploitation. However, there is no direct application of it on the insurance act where subject matter of services and contract are related thereto. Insurance is a kind of a safety package in form of various policies that every individual seeks in order to protect them/their belongings from any financial losses/damages from the future events whereas under the CPA redressal is provided if such consumer is aggrieved from the acts of the insurer in regard with those policies. Commission/courts are established at national, state & district level to resolve the disputes between the parties. With the remedies being made available and the amendments being brought into the ombudsman scheme have provided policyholders some sort of relief in terms of disposing off their complaints at the earliest. As seen from the case laws mere delay in intimating the theft /damage of the products under policy with probable reasonable ground so given doesn't refute the claims of the policyholders. Being negligent and unfair in performing the services by the insurer such as non- settlement of claims, shortcoming in fulfilling their intention or misleading the policies in order to exploit the insured amounts to Deficiencies of services by these insurance company which in line have their repercussions causing mental harassments and hardships on their overall life and thus leading in impairing the justice system. Therefore, in my personal opinion it is very much needed to strength the laws regarding the insurance company and provide better redressal mechanism for speedy disposal of the complaints of the aggrieved party. The Move made by the IDAI in regards of the amendments made in insurance Ombudsman scheme is technologically innovative in this ever so changing/growing society. This won't only solve the dispute but will also help policyholders and at the same go supervision/cases over the actions of all the agents/insurers/brokers of an insurance company under one regulatory hood can be dealt with effectively.

CHAPTER-VII

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